

BETWEEN POLITICS AND INCONVENIENT EVIDENCE

Assessing the Renewed EU Action Plan
against migrant smuggling

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Between politics and inconvenient evidence:

Assessing the Renewed EU Action Plan against migrant smuggling

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**Order alphabetical*

Abstract

Following the European Commission's recent release of its Renewed EU Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling (2021-2025), we take stock of key insights arising from recent and ongoing research on the facilitation of irregular migration. The EU's counter-smuggling policies equate irregular migration to a crime, while disregarding that safe, orderly and regular pathways for refugees and other migrants are hard to access. The Renewed EU Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling (2021-2025) exacerbates the risks that refugees and other migrants face by penalising those who assist them. Civil society actors, family members and communities that act out of compassion or provide basic services in transit and destination countries continue to be investigated and prosecuted as 'migrant smugglers'.

We call for more nuanced policy responses to migrant smuggling that are compliant with human rights and backed by empirical research. We recommend that the European Commission conducts a thorough human rights impact assessment of this Renewed EU Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling and related Anti-Smuggling Operational Partnerships with third countries. The EU must narrow down its criminal definition of 'facilitation of irregular migration' to conform with the UN Migrant Smuggling protocol's protection of family members, humanitarians and other bona fide actors by including an 'unjust enrichment' motive. We reiterate that all smuggled refugees and other migrants, regardless of how they reach their destination, must be exempt from criminalisation. We stress that returns, entry-bans and pushbacks should never be seen as counter-smuggling measures as they only increase the demand for migrant smuggling. Thus, we call on EU policy makers to create and enhance safe, orderly and regular pathways in light of the commitments under the UN Global Compacts for Migration and on Refugees.

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- **Gabriella Sanchez** (Texas A&M International University);
- **Eugenio Cusumano** (Marie Curie Fellow at the University of Venice);
- **Roxane de Massol de Rebetz** (PhD candidate, Leiden School of Law, Leiden University);
- **Roberto Forin** (Global Programme Coordinator at Mixed Migration Centre (MMC) that is part of the Danish Refugee Council (DRC));
- **Michele LeVoy** (Director of Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants (PICUM)).

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1. Introduction

‘Migrant smuggling’ became a primary argument underpinning the EU’s recent accusations concerning Belarus’ channelling of refugees and other migrants to the EU’s external borders solely for political gain. However, what do we really know about the EU’s counter-smuggling policies and about the phenomenon itself?

In light of the European Commission’s newly published [Renewed EU Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling \(2021-2025\)](#), this Policy Brief provides key insights from recent empirical research on the facilitation of irregular migration and migrant smuggling in the EU and Mediterranean region.[‡] An increasing number of academic voices [challenge the claim](#) that the facilitation of irregular migration and migrant smuggling is solely the domain of mafias and [transnational criminal organisations](#)¹. Evidence points to the existence of a more diverse group of actors – including migrants and refugees themselves – rather than those exclusively motivated by profit.

Furthermore, evidence underlines a growing trend of the EU Member States criminalising self-organised migration and designating acts of solidarity as ‘migrant smuggling’. In other words, the evidence raises concerns over how EU counter-smuggling policies, laws, and practices that allegedly target ‘criminal organisations’ instead impact both refugees and other migrants trying to reach safer destinations, and those who provide them with humanitarian assistance.

Rising numbers of migrants, asylum seekers and refugees have no option other than to rely on smugglers to reach places of safety, places where they can ask for international protection or to unite with their families. Research shows that due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the number of refugees and other migrants that are unable to cover smuggling fees and instead self-relocate and self-organise their journeys increased². Alongside these are individuals who provide assistance – family members, friends, ordinary people and civil society actors – who also find themselves caught in the crossfire of rigorous counter-smuggling measures and the often politically charged legal environment associated with them.

This Policy Brief cautions against the contemporary political reliance on simplistic narratives about ‘migrant smuggling’ that intentionally ignore inconvenient evidence on the negative impacts of counter-smuggling activities on refugees and other migrants, and those who assist them. In line with the [UN Smuggling Protocol](#), we encourage policymakers to avoid actions that victimise people on the move, refugees and other migrants, their families, and those who extend them rescue, support or basic services³ (see sections 2 and 4).

[‡] In this policy brief, we distinguish notions of ‘facilitation of irregular migration’ from ‘migrant smuggling’. The European Commission defines, in its Facilitation Directive, that anyone who ‘intentionally assists’ any third country nationals to enter, transit or reside into the EU territory without necessary documentation, can be considered as ‘facilitator of irregular migration’. The UN Smuggling Protocol defines ‘migrant smuggling’ as a crime when it is done for ‘financial or other material benefit motive’.

From its inception, the UN Migrant Smuggling Protocol was drafted with a clear focus on countering the for-profit facilitation of smuggling. Still, civil society and ordinary citizens within the EU increasingly face formal criminalisation and a wider range of sanctions and policing practices – including suspicion and [harassment and intimidation](#) – when acting in solidarity with refugees and other migrants in transit⁴. Carrera et al. have termed this phenomenon the ‘policing of humanitarianism’ and point out the growing criminal designation of these activities as ‘crimes of facilitation’, raising concerns over the EU’s counter-smuggling laws and policies’ compatibility with the UN Protocol (see sections 3 and 5).

Before the release of the [Renewed Action Plan](#), a [commentary](#) from Ylva Johansson, the European Commissioner for Home Affairs, suggested that the new plan would not significantly deviate in focus from the preceding [2015-2020 action plan](#)⁵. Indeed, such expectations proved accurate. The ‘new’ plan continues to ignore the evidence and the experiences of those directly impacted by counter-smuggling policies, thereby allowing for the continued criminalisation of migrants, their community members, and humanitarian actors in the EU and beyond.

In what follows, we call for much-needed engagement with the empirical research and a closer examination of the impacts of counter-smuggling policy and practice on the lives of refugees and other migrants in transit (see sections 6-8).

Our recommendations propose that a narrow focus on the criminality of ‘migrant smuggling’ risks precluding some long-term assessments on how the EU’s visa, migration and asylum policies co-create a demand for migrant smuggling. We call on EU policy makers to consider increasing the accessibility and availability of safe, orderly and regular channels for refugees and other migrants, in light of the commitments in the UN Global Compacts for Migration and on Refugees.

2. EU narratives of ‘migrant smuggling’

The European Commission, in both the [2015-2020 Action Plan](#) and the [preparation](#) of the new Action Plan, consistently portrayed the facilitation of migrant smuggling as a profit-motivated, often violent, and sophisticated form of organised crime controlled by transnational networks⁶. The Renewed Action plan itself continues to rely on the same simplistic narratives that characterise smuggled refugees and other migrants as agency-less victims and imagine a false dichotomy wherein ‘good’ state policies must be implemented to ‘save’ them from ‘bad’ smugglers.

The Renewed Action Plan argues that the fundamental rights of refugees and other migrants are only violated by smugglers, ignoring the role of state-perpetrated pushbacks and pullbacks at creating risk⁷. Furthermore, the Renewed Action Plan portrays all the purchasers of smuggling services as illegitimate asylum seekers by referencing their rates of return⁸. It states the unreferenced statistic that ‘two thirds of [irregular migrants reaching the EU] do not meet the criteria for being granted international protection and will eventually need to be returned’.

We argue that the false dichotomy of 'good refugees' and 'bad irregular migrants' serves as a distraction from the instrumentalised use of criminal justice to prevent and penalise any irregular arrivals. It also wrongly assumes that quick returns will discourage people from buying such services (see section 6).

EU policymakers have long depicted transnational smuggling organisations as the [drivers of irregular migration](#), systematically blaming them for the precarious journeys and tragedies endured by refugees and other migrants in transit, rather than recognising the lack of safe, regular and orderly pathways to migration and asylum as the key catalysts driving the demand for smuggling services⁹. While EU Commissioner Ylva Johansson [blamed](#) smugglers for the lives lost at sea¹⁰, EU remains silent about the inaccessibility of Schengen visas, and the way that the EU's [Carrier Sanctions Directive](#)¹¹ prevents any transportation companies from providing their services to refugees and other migrants who do not have valid travel documents and visas to arrive into the EU.

Among other developments, the Renewed Action Plan includes references to the 'state-sponsored smuggling of migrants' when reacting to what was the escalating situation between Belarus and the EU's Member States from July 2021 onwards.¹² The Renewed EU Action Plan stated that 'migrant smugglers have taken advantage of the situation', however, many services were regular and provided by legitimate companies. In response to the escalating situation with Belarus, several [airlines were threatened with EU sanctions](#) should they facilitate flights for people who travel to Belarus, even when they have valid documents and visas¹³. One especially controversial action was the decision by some airlines to restrict certain nationals from their flights, such as Syrians, Afghans, Yemenis and Iraqis, precisely because they are more likely to be asylum seekers.

It is apparent how the EU's counter-smuggling actions become a euphemism for preventing people who may seek international protection in the EU to travel safely within third countries. Academics have observed similar dynamics in Niger, among other examples, where counter-smuggling policies severely restrict individuals' possibilities to look for employment or protection in neighbouring countries¹⁴. The newly outlined 'Anti-Smuggling Operational Partnerships' with third countries foreseen in the Renewed Action Plan may thus inadvertently increase the demand for smuggling services.¹⁵ The European Ombudsman previously called on the European Commission to ensure that human rights impact assessment are conducted when cooperating with third countries on various sensitive migration management related issues, such as those foreseen in the 'EU-Turkey' statement, and the same should apply to any new partnerships¹⁶.

Both the [previous](#) and the [Renewed](#) Action Plan create a narrative artificially linking migrant smuggling with other forms of crime such as human trafficking for sexual and labour exploitation, drugs and weapons trafficking, and even terrorism¹⁷. EU policymakers' narratives

often cite harrowing examples of sexual exploitation and abuse where African women figure prominently as reasons to counteract migrant smuggling at any cost, intentionally dismissing the evidence that indicates that trafficking for sexual purposes into Europe relies on other mechanisms and actors¹⁸. Refraining from simplistically conflating migrant smuggling and human trafficking with sex work is crucial for identifying the risks migrants and refugees are likely to face on their journeys. Furthermore, the focus on African women as the only targets of sexual violence on the migration pathway reveals the ways in which their bodies have been historically fetishised by European audiences. This obscures the wide variety of gender-based violence that women, girls and boys and even men face during their journeys¹⁹.

Moreover, despite the abundance of allegations against ‘ruthless smugglers’, efforts to trace other crimes and abuses to migration enforcement and control are scant, such as when states conduct [illegal pushbacks](#)²⁰. The facilitation of journeys is not inherently criminal, and narratives purporting the intrinsic or systematic linkages of migrant smuggling with other crimes have been strongly contested by [academic research](#)²¹. Examples from across the Sahel and North Africa show how historical forms of transportation across the region have suddenly found themselves designated as ‘smuggling’, destroying the [livelihoods](#) of entire communities in the process²².

Official narratives also reproduce gendered and racist depictions of smugglers as violent men of colour. This strips the collective nature of mobility efforts. [Women and extended families](#) play pivotal roles in the facilitation of migrants’ journeys²³. Families host migrants in transit and care for those who become injured or sick. Women coordinate segments of migrants’ journeys and in some instances also transport them across vast distances. Young people and children also contribute to these collective efforts that benefit their families and communities. Many pay off their journeys by carrying out smuggling-related tasks that range from acting as lookouts and recruiting other migrants to piloting boats across the Mediterranean²⁴.

None of these statements seek to suggest that those behind migrants’ irregular journeys should be seen solely as benevolent actors. What we argue is that by rendering invisible the community dynamics that allow for the mobility of migrants and by endorsing the organised crime paradigm, EU policymakers have criminalised long-standing [human mobility](#) practices across the Southern Neighbourhood, justifying the deployment of criminal justice tools for migration management purposes in the name of EU border security²⁵.

Shifting the narratives of the facilitation of irregular migration away from criminality and violence alone allows us to [refocus](#) on viable solutions, such as creating equally accessible, regular, safe and orderly [paths towards the EU](#) in line with the Global Compact for Migration and Global Compact on Refugees²⁶.

3. Vague criminal definition as a Pandora's Box

The EU Member States' conflate criminal definitions of 'migrant smuggling' and 'the facilitation of irregular migration'. As we demonstrate below, they require different standards of proof for individuals' prosecution. The [UN Migrant Smuggling Protocol](#) clearly delineates smuggling as having a '...financial or other material benefit' motive²⁷. The UNODC outlined that 'the Protocol does not seek – and cannot be used as the legal basis for – the prosecution of those acting with humanitarian intent or on the basis of close family ties where there is no purpose to obtain a financial or other material benefit'. This was strongly reiterated by the UNODC's 2004 [Legislative Guide](#) on the Protocol's implementation and its 2017 [Issue Paper](#) on the 'Financial or Other Material Benefit'²⁸.

Yet, the European Union's [Facilitation Directive](#), created [broader opportunities for prosecution](#) by criminalising the facilitation of 'entry and transit' without requiring any proof of benefit to the 'facilitators'²⁹. The for-profit motive is required for the facilitation of irregular stay and residence, however it is not respected in the legislation of [half of the EU's Member States](#)³⁰. Such Member States' neglect of profit motive in both their legislation and practice is incompatible with the UN Migrant Smuggling Protocol and opens Pandora's box for prosecuting various *bona fide* actors.

In 2020, the European Commission issued [Guidance on implementing the Facilitation Directive](#) which accompanied the [EU Pact on Migration and Asylum](#). The Guidance recognises that the Migrant Smuggling Protocol does not intend to criminalise the actions of humanitarian actors and migrants' family members supporting their mobility. However, this only comes as a 'Commission Communication' and thus is not legally binding on the Member States³¹. The Guidance recommends that Member States create exemptions for the humanitarian acts 'mandated by law,' however it made those acts conditional on 'ensuring effective migration management in compliance with relevant legal obligations.'³² Although the Guidance acknowledged that Search-and-Rescue (SAR) activities fall under the clear obligation of international law, private SAR actors are subjected to [additional safety rules and regulations](#), under a separate Commission recommendation, as if to imply that their actions were the ones posing risks to refugees and other migrants³³.

The Guidance fails to distinguish that these not-for-profit actors aim to uphold the rights of others. It also fails to protect the right to provide humanitarian assistance and other services to undocumented migrants, as it allows Member States to decide which acts are 'mandated by law' on a 'case-by-case basis.' Any legitimate civil society and/or business activity aimed at assisting refugees and other migrants risks being prosecuted as a crime of 'facilitation of irregular migration', until the respective court drops the criminal charges due to the absence of criminal intent. Thus, there is an urgent need for a 'firewall' that protects the independent mandate of human rights defenders, or even of business owners, who provide basic services, from prosecution and also from being obliged to act on behalf of migration controls³⁴.

Under current EU law, the facilitation of entry, transit and residence of asylum seekers is also not exempted. In this case, Member States can still prosecute on a ‘case-by-case basis’ as to verify ‘whether an act has been mandated by law’. This stands at odds with the Geneva Convention’s Article 31, which declares that asylum seekers should not be penalised for their irregular entry and, by extension of this non-penalisation provision, neither should those who help them.

A recent [CJEU case against Hungary](#) gives some hope, as a person who assists migrants “in making or lodging an application for asylum to the competent national authorities, even if he or she knows that that application cannot be successful, cannot be compared with a person providing assistance with unauthorised entry, transit or residence, such as that referred to in Article 1(1) of Directive 2002/90.”³⁵

4. Blurred distinctions between victims and perpetrators

A lack of clear legal delineation between activities that constitute the crime of migrant smuggling and the crime of human trafficking is another challenge. The EU’s incongruous narratives and legal interpretations of international legal frameworks adds to the confusion. Individual actors within legal systems, such as judges and prosecutors, have much discretion. They may end up over criminalising smuggled migrants and those who assist them whilst harm motives are entirely absent.

In her work with Belgian prosecutors, de Massol de Rebetz shows that judges have a hard time grasping the complexity of refugees and migrants’ situations, who are often involved in roles related to the facilitation of irregular migration³⁶. Prosecutors had different approaches. One, for example, claimed that a case in which a migrant received free passage for a leg of their journey constituted a clear example of the UN Migrant Smuggling Protocol’s material benefit. Another prosecutor contrastingly considered that the migrant involved in the facilitation of irregular migration should be considered victims of human trafficking. The prosecutor invoked non-punishment clause present in the EU’s anti-trafficking legal framework to protect refugees and other migrants, as they perceived traces of exploitation and abuse in situations of vulnerability. Experts in the field explained that the precarious status of many individuals stranded while *en route* could make it difficult for them to refuse an offer to collaborate with smugglers that could facilitate their further transit, despite its illicit nature³⁷.

These disparate opinions on the part of prosecutors illustrate the dangers created by a lack of clear and consistently enforceable standards in the EU.

Article 5 of the Smuggling Protocol states that migrants who rely on smuggling to reach safety should not be charged with the crime themselves. Nevertheless, the legal record shows that a significant number of refugees and other migrants have been prosecuted as smugglers for [facilitating segments](#) of their own journeys³⁸. For instance, a [Syrian man was sentenced](#) to 52 years in prison for ‘facilitating illegal entry’ after piloting a vessel with other refugees and migrants from Turkey to the Greek island of Chios. In Italy, as a consequence of prosecutors rely upon ‘smuggler profiles’, ‘the majority of people charged with the crime of smuggling have been

[migrants who were steering and holding the compass](#) on the boat carrying irregular migrants to Europe³⁹.

Per the Smuggling Protocol, family members who participate in the facilitation of the journey of a relative for no profit should not face prosecution. Nevertheless, a UNODC report⁴⁰ shows that courts across the EU systematically [charge](#) relatives (many times, the wives and mothers of migrants) with smuggling for facilitating the journeys of their [family members](#)⁴¹. Media reports further illustrate the trend. For example, an [Afghan man was charged](#) with having endangered his son's life after the latter died in transit while traveling alongside with him from Turkey to Greece⁴². Similarly, a [Senegalese man was charged](#) with complicity in the smuggling of migrants after financing his son's voyage⁴³.

Various discussions with law enforcement and criminal justice practitioners confirmed that punishing such 'low-key actors' 'has no visible impact on dismantling or disrupting the *smuggling business model*⁵, but can only lead to more risks for victims of smuggling⁴⁴.' Regrettably, the trend of '[picking the low hanging fruit](#)' by prosecuting refugees and other migrants, their family members and civil society will likely continue under the Renewed Action Plan, because Member States can use this 'Pandora's Box' clause to prosecute the facilitation of entry without any profit motive, and were only 'invited' not to criminalise humanitarian assistance⁴⁵.

The Renewed Action Plan quotes that, 'in 2020, actions in the framework of EMPACT resulted in 2 110 international investigations, 2 280 arrests, of which 16 high-value targets, the identification of 27 and dismantling of 14 criminal networks⁴⁶.' The overall number of high value targets and criminal groups appears extremely low, in comparison with the number of overall arrests. In this context, the further push [for 1 400 anti-smuggling prosecutions](#) in 2022 is highly concerning, because refugees and other migrants, as well as their family members and civil society actors, could be targeted to meet this artificial quota⁴⁷.

The [Renewed Action Plan](#) states that a report on the implementation of the Guidance will be released in 2023, and indicates the revision of the Directive will take place 'if necessary⁴⁸.' The seriousness of the cases already identified by researchers indicate we cannot wait until 2023. While this indicates an openness to changing policy, the lack of concrete commitments or immediate action is long overdue, as [numerous](#) studies have [confirmed](#) that the EU Facilitation Directive is [unfit](#) for purpose⁴⁹.

⁵ Authors are critical towards the existence of a hierarchical and highly organised criminal migrant smuggling business model. There may be 'business models' that prove viable for specific actors in a certain geographic context during a set period of time, yet scholarship evinces that concepts of a single homogenous 'business model' of migrant smuggling are a political tool often used to justify policies of containment. See Sanchez et al. (2021), '[Current Trends and Challenges on the Facilitation of Irregular Migration in Tunisia, Algeria and Morocco](#)' for more information.

However, the [Renewed Action Plan](#) does reiterate that smuggled migrants can enjoy rights under the Victims' Rights Directive 'independently of their residence status', and correctly states that 'migrants should not become liable to criminal prosecution for having been smuggled⁵⁰'.

One EU effort intended to protect 'victims' rights' is the issuing of residence permits to migrants who cooperate as part of counter-smuggling investigations. Yet, serious questions remain regarding the extent to which obtaining such permits is contingent upon cooperation with authorities, and whether such cooperation requirements force irregular migrants to name their peers as facilitators to avoid deportation. These questions merit further analysis in the new study on the Residence Permit Directive that the European Commission has committed to launching in the Renewed Action Plan.

5. Safeguarding the right to humanitarian assistance and basic services

The [EU Facilitation Directive](#) poses risks for those [upholding the human rights of refugees and other migrants](#),⁵¹ as the [Guidance](#) released in 2020 did not provide a clear definition of the crime⁵². Research conducted as a component of the EU-funded Horizon 2020 [ReSOMA Project](#) found that in the period between 2015-19, this lack of legal clarity led to the arrest or conviction of at least 150 volunteers, humanitarians and human rights defenders, including some NGO members, family members of refugees and migrants, mayors, and priests, for activities related to helping undocumented migrants with no financial or material benefit⁵³.

This criminalisation of solidarity continues. Sean Binder and Sarah Mardini are among 24 humanitarian actors going on trial in Greece for charges of smuggling and espionage, facing multiple years in prison⁵⁴. Additionally, the first criminalisation of solidarity in Lithuania concerned assistance provided to asylum seekers from Afghanistan. A Lithuanian woman hosted five asylum seekers, while they were waiting for the European Court of Human Rights' (ECHR) decision on interim measures so that they would not be pushed back by the state into Belarus. The Strasbourg Court issued the order, however, that the young woman is now suspected of facilitating their irregular stay in Lithuania⁵⁵.

The EU Facilitation Directive also criminalises the provision of basic services to undocumented migrants. The widespread risk of prosecution among civil society actors and basic service providers is thus restricting their societal inclusion and encouraging [racial profiling](#)⁵⁶. For example, because of such fears, landlords are [less likely to rent](#) an apartment/house not only to undocumented migrants, but to anyone of colour, including nationals and EU citizens⁵⁷.

Law enforcement actors often portray the provision of transportation or housing services to undocumented migrants as related to migrant smuggling/facilitation of irregular migration. For instance, a Europol report suggested a person could 'unintentionally' facilitate smuggling if failing to check a person's immigration documents prior to the provision of a service, converting ordinary citizens into *de facto* migration enforcers. Thus, [taxi or Blabla car drivers or Airbnb hosts risk being charged](#) with crimes of facilitating irregular migration⁵⁸. Not only can this

increase the risks for racial discrimination in peer-to-peer services, but this also creates a specific gap in the services market that may be filled by actors willing to profit from the specific vulnerabilities of asylum seekers and undocumented migrants.

6. The self-organisation of irregular journeys: Lessons from North Africa

In the EU, the facilitation of irregular migration is most often depicted as under the domain of international criminal networks of smugglers. Evidence from the field systematically challenges this claim. There is a wide range of ways in which irregular journeys are launched and/or organised. In fact, the [facilitation of irregular journeys](#) is often not motivated by profit. For example, Kheira Arrouche's work in Algeria, one of the main departure points of irregular migration in North Africa, indicates that neither smuggling networks nor other forms of transnationally organised criminality as defined by the EU appear to play a significant role in the irregular journeys of sub-Saharan migrants and Algerian nationals⁵⁹. Their journeys are instead primarily community-based efforts to generate income amid the economic crisis.

'Sub-Saharan migrants**' do rely on facilitators or brokers operating in border communities in the region with cross-border and seafaring knowledge⁶⁰. These are the key actors providing transportation and accommodation services. They also provide essential information on routes, destinations, cities with employment opportunities etc., which determines the next stage of migrants' journey.

Border communities have increasingly engaged in these practices following the deterioration of their socio-economic livelihood in line with the intensive criminalisation of migration across Algerian borders due to the instability of the region (mainly the outbreak of the conflict in Mali and Libya⁶¹). In the African context, [Spijkerboer](#) argues that the concepts of 'irregular migration' and 'migrant smuggling' are 'are seen as an effect of the exclusion of migrants from human rights protection imposed on African policymakers by European pressure⁶².' Unfortunately, migration governance policies in the Sahel region disregard the socio-economic landscape and the way in which community actors' roles derive from the complex realities on the ground (for instance, the longstanding provision of mobility along the Niger-Libya route⁶³). Thus, facilitators or brokers residing in border communities leverage their territorial navigation knowledge, migratory experiences, and social contacts to arrange migrant crossings. Most of them engage in the market for migrant smuggling to sustain their livelihoods and living conditions, [without direct convergence](#) with other groups like drug traffickers or terrorists⁶⁴.

** We place quotation marks surrounding this term given the way it has been used to designate a racialised population and as part of the larger construction of blackness in Africa. For a discussion, see Leslie Gross-Wyrtzen and Lorena Gazzotti's [writing](#) in the [special issue](#) of The Journal of North African Studies, Volume 26, Issue 5 (2021) 'Telling Histories of the Present: Postcolonial Perspectives on Morocco's 'Radically New' Migration Policy'.

Further insights from ethnographic fieldwork demonstrate that migrants perceive smugglers as information gatekeepers and not necessarily as mobility providers⁶⁵. Migrants articulated their efforts to reduce their reliance on smuggling services as attempts to maintain their agency and autonomy over their mobility trajectories. Migrants are aware of the restrictive and dangerous crossing conditions through the Sahel region and do their best to avoid the use of smuggling services by instead relying on their own data gathering efforts. For instance, prior to departing, individuals planning transnational migration journeys collect information from friends or previous migrants, both of whom might recommend particular smugglers of good repute. Migrants may then employ this information to migrate through longer routes and countries where they can move independently or with the support of fellow migrants along the route and residents of border communities, thereby avoiding the purchase of smuggler services.

This kind of information gathering is evident in the case of migrants traveling from Sub-Saharan African countries and reaching southern Algeria – specifically the city of Tamanrasset. The city is considered an important site along larger migration journeys not merely because of the presence of brokers or mobility facilitators, but also as a location where a large community of individuals pushed back by the Algerian authorities gather. Those waiting to move northwards and those settled in the south all share key information and resources. Armed with fresh, reliable information and contacts, most migrants opt for alternative ways to move north, such as traveling by bus or train, and in the process avoiding smuggler services entirely⁶⁶.

In the same vein, North African migrants often undertake similar [self-organised irregular journeys](#) in reaction to the lack of legal pathways for migration⁶⁷. The ability to organise such journeys stems from individuals' social contacts – family, friends, neighbours, and diaspora communities. The evidence of individuals avoiding professional or organised smuggling services challenges the official narratives that construct smuggling service providers as drivers of migration. Claims common in counter-smuggling policies tend to criminalise self-organised journeys as facilitated by organised crime, and thus create heightened legitimisation of counter-smuggling strategies. There is thus a clear need to move away from security and containment policies of migration at the borders, for they expose migrants to precarity by increasing the inaccessibility of safe, orderly and regular pathways for mobility.

7. The role of returns: Lessons from North Africa

Contrary to what the EU's [Roadmap](#) to implement the New Pact on Migration and Asylum argues, returns do not discourage migrant smuggling⁶⁸. In the context of Algeria, the state approaches and views the irregular migration of refugees and other migrants within Algeria through a criminalisation lens, which constructs the presence of undocumented migrants as a threat to national order and a source of crime, disease, and drugs. The Algerian state's policies, introduced under pressure from the EU on all North African countries to contain the irregular migration through their territory, [criminalise irregular migration](#) of both citizens and non-citizens⁶⁹. For this purpose, the authorities run weekly mass deportation activities (*le*

refoulement') from all over northern Algerian cities to the southern borders with Niger in ways that target refugees and other migrants. The case of Algerian nationals intercepted embarking on irregular journeys is not that different. 'Irregular migrants' face [up to six months in prison and high fines](#)⁷⁰.

These procedures involving collective expulsions from Algeria fail to meet humanitarian standards, as noted by the [United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights](#), given the country's lack of an adequate human rights protection system⁷¹. Algerian authorities justify these operations as part of an official agreement with Nigerien authorities to deport their citizens. However, the expulsion operations disregard both the nationalities of the migrants and their status as asylum seekers or refugees, with families and their children often becoming separated in the process. Refugees and other migrants transiting through Algeria point out that the intensive discrimination, violence, and inhumane conditions they face during these expulsions additionally compound with the perilous conditions in the inhospitable desert.

Despite their draconian nature, none of these practices effectively deter irregular migration. Sub-Saharan migrants, once left at the borders, often return to the city of Tamanrasset to launch their journeys back to cities like Oran or Algiers yet again. The same happens with refugees and other migrants expelled from Morocco to Algeria, who, upon being deported to the city of Oran, prepare for their return to Morocco. In Algeria, while refugees and other migrants living under this expulsion regime describe it as exhausting, they also report saving for such contingencies, or to count on the support of family and friends in anticipation of such challenges. Granted, many others lose their savings during deportation or raid processes, but this is seen as inherent challenge of being an irregular migrant in the country.

What is significant here is that, despite being sent back numerous times, most refugees and other migrants still find a way back to northern Algeria. Indeed, refugees and other migrants stressed that they would return to Algeria even if they were 'deported a thousand times'⁷². It is also worth noting that these practices are not unique to 'Sub-Saharan migrants' but are also performed by those who have been involuntarily deported from the EU to their countries of origin.

The penalties imposed on Algerian nationals, refugees and other migrants seem to have scant impact on their determination to attempt to leave the country again, considering the deteriorating economic and political situation in Algeria. Thus, neither incarceration nor fines diminish one's will to migrate again. Similar evidence provided by civil society representatives in the EU explains that Union-wide entry bans following returns from the EU, created by the 2008 [EU Return Directive](#) and reiterated in the proposed 2018 [Recast](#), may actually increase the demand for and professionalisation of smuggling service providers⁷³.

8. Corruption and the facilitation of migrant smuggling

Policy approaches often neglect to address the ways in which corruption enables migrant smuggling and irregular migration. Empirical evidence has shown that clandestine border crossings are also often the result of the complicity of state authorities in third countries and within the EU itself⁷⁴. But corruption does not emerge in a vacuum. Policies that expand the presence and power of state security apparatuses on Europe's external borders risk creating opportunities for members of border enforcement agencies and political apparatuses to financially benefit.

Furthermore, one must keep in mind the economic disparities faced by law enforcement in third countries, and their long standing precarity as agents of the state. Border agents, in particular, rely on bribes and other kickbacks to both supplement their salaries, and maintain amicable interactions with locals⁷⁵. As the Algerian and Tunisian cases show, maintaining a dual discourse – one that in public condemns smuggling, while allowing smugglers to operate relatively free of restrictions within their territories – has often been a strategy adopted by governments across North Africa.⁷⁶ This ensures the appearance of compliance and alignment with EU migration control priorities, while simultaneously maintaining the stability and sustainability of border communities to a degree, whose members rely on the smuggling of goods, services and people to reduce a deeply engrained landscape of widespread marginalisation and exclusion⁷⁷.

The EU institutions, agencies, as well as EU Member States and their officials, are also not immune to corruption or other human rights violations. For instance, the Belgian Secretary of State for Asylum, Migration and Administrative Simplification, Theo Francken, was involved in [a corruption scandal](#) after he opened an opaque humanitarian visa channel that was operated by private intermediaries that reportedly took high fees from the individuals concerned⁷⁸. The strength of applicants' asylum claims was not duly ensured through this channel, therefore coordinating it can be seen as profit motivated based on the EU's rigid understanding these activities.

There are also examples at the EU level. For instance, in 2018 the EU's anti-fraud office OLAF found various irregularities and financial mismanagement of the European Asylum Support Office (EASO⁷⁹). Frontex has been under numerous investigations, including by OLAF, related to misconduct, harassment and violations of the rights of refugees and other migrants, which would also translate into the inefficient use of the EU's resources in light of the [EU's Better Regulation Guidelines](#)⁸⁰.

9. Conclusions

The Renewed EU Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling (2021-2025) fails to admit that European Union counter-smuggling efforts have had counterproductive effects. EU policymakers cannot continue to rely on the recirculation of narratives that are not based on evidence and promise miraculous outcomes.

In the Central Mediterranean, the [2015-2020 Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling](#) aimed to increase the penalties for those facilitating irregular migration⁸¹. Yet, policies continue failing to admit that the criminalisation of mobility efforts have instead increasingly put the safety of refugees and other migrants at risk while compromising the precarious livelihoods of their communities and those through which their transit. For example, the [2015-2020 Action Plan](#), by identifying, capturing, and disposing of vessels used by smugglers, simply led smugglers to rely on cheaper and more unseaworthy vessels. It in turn [increased the risk of voyages across the Central Mediterranean](#), on the basis of the recorded numbers of arrivals and death that show that the mortality rate on this route seemed to peak from June 2018 to August 2019. This coincided with the period in which no SAR operations from NGOs or EU state assets were present at sea⁸². Critical research on deaths along the southern EU borders warns that this rate is hard to estimate, as many deaths, as well as clandestine arrivals, are not captured by current statistics⁸³.

The increase in border control and surveillance on the one hand, and reduced opportunities for safe and regular migration on the other, have inadvertently expanded the market for irregular migration and shifted the facilitation of smuggling services to rely on more dangerous techniques.

Counter-smuggling action should avoid conflating lifesaving activities with criminal offenses. Effective policies recognise migrants' autonomy, solidarity efforts, and the structural causes of irregular migration, reducing existing impediments to mobility rather than further criminalising transborder movements. None of these dynamics are adequately represented in the Renewed EU Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling (2021-2025).

Furthermore, the reliance on return practices (already shown to have limited if any impact on deterrence) and the failure to identify the structural factors that contribute to corruption among enforcement officials, suggest that the drafters of the new Action Plan may have no intention to correct course.

To be effective, the implementation of the Renewed EU Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling (2021-2025) will need to include human rights impact assessments on the potential for heightened criminalisation and counter the insufficient accessibility to justice by both undocumented migrants and migration-affected communities. However, none of these measures were included in the Renewed Action Plan, but for the inclusion of what seems a vague, planned evaluation of the Guidance on the Facilitation Directive's implementation, to be released in 2023 – which is too far into the future.

There is abundant evidence available to policymakers concerning the dynamics of mobility in the Southern Neighbourhood and within Europe. Criminalising human mobility without addressing refugees and other migrants' protection needs constitutes a clear neglect of states' own obligations under international human rights and humanitarian law.

10. Policy recommendations

1. Counter-smuggling policies such as the Renewed Action Plan must avoid relying on narratives convenient to legitimise political choices. To be effective, policy must be informed not only by the various datasets of respected international institutions and NGOs, but also by the empirical evidence coming from qualitative academic research that includes the perspectives of those directly impacted by policy decisions. These include smuggled migrants, transit and destination communities, and civil society working on the ground.
2. In line with Article 5 of the UN Migrant Smuggling Protocol, the EU's counter-smuggling policies must ensure the rights of all migrants and refugees, including both those who rely on the services of smugglers and those who independently facilitate their own journeys and their families. Smuggled migrants should never be criminalised, regardless of who has been their facilitator. They should be treated as victims under the EU Victims' Rights Directive and issued residence papers throughout the process.
3. The European Commission must conduct a thorough human rights impact assessment of the Renewed EU Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling (2021-2025). The EU must also ensure such an assessment for each Anti-Smuggling Operational Partnership with third countries, as it has been previously required by the European Ombudsman.
4. Counter-smuggling initiatives and policies must never criminalise humanitarian and human rights activities. The EU legislation should include 'firewall' principle that protects human rights defenders, be they civil society organisations, volunteers, journalists, or even business owners, who provide basic services from prosecutions and from being obliged to act on behalf of migration controls. Sea rescues and any other humanitarian activities under international humanitarian law carried out by civil society and other actors should also not be made conditional on cooperation with national or EU law enforcement agencies in migration management.
5. The definition of the crime of 'facilitation of irregular migration' needs to be narrowed down and brought back in line with the UN Migrant Smuggling Protocol. Law enforcement actors should only aim at the high-profile prosecutions, and when there are clear unjust enrichment motives. This way the EU's counter-smuggling initiatives would also avoid chasing after 'low-hanging fruit' or over criminalising various other legitimate activities. Thus, Individuals and private business (i.e. landlords, taxis) should also be permitted to provide their services to everyone who requests them, without having to demand proof of immigration status, which would encourage racial profiling and discrimination.

6. EU policymakers must stop using returns as an anti-smuggling measure. Counter-smuggling and return policies should not be used to prevent or discourage the arrival of refugees and other migrants, who may have subsidiary protection needs, or seek to join their family members. Empirical fieldwork illustrates that returns fail, as refugees and other migrants often re-organise new attempts after deportation and removal, even when they are pushed back, expelled or returned to countries of transit or origin.
7. Often, the right to seek asylum and obtain international protection in the EU is only accessible through the use of smuggling services and irregular means. Thus, EU policymakers need to expand equally accessible, safe, orderly and regular pathways to asylum and migration, in light of the objectives committed in the Global Compact for Migration and Global Compact on Refugees as to reduce the demand for migrant smuggling services. This would also prevent further opportunities for third countries and malign actors to place migrants in danger by operationalising their migration policy for political influence, attempted by Belarus most recently, and also previously by Turkey, Morocco, Libya and others.

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